

Report on number of stakeholders engaged within the project

Deliverable 2.2

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
APRE	Agency for the Promotion of European Research
EMÜ	Estonian University of Life Sciences
FBCD	Food and Bio Cluster Denmark
MAA	Multi-Actor Approach
NIBIO	Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research
SB	Stakeholders' Board
RISE	Research Institute of Sweden
UNIPA	University of Palermo
WP	Work Package

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1 Executive Summary

This document provides a comprehensive overview of the stakeholder engagement activities implemented throughout the BlueRev project. BlueRev aims to drive social and environmentally sustainable changes within and beyond local communities across three pilot regions (Denmark and Greenland, Italy, Estonia) by establishing sustainable and socially responsible business, governance and social innovation models in the blue bio-based sector.

Throughout the three-years duration of the project, engaging relevant stakeholders was crucial to achieving BlueRev's objectives: the activities performed led to the involvement of almost 1000 actors with diverse background and expertise, who contributed through participation in co-creation sessions and interviews, took part in both in-person and online training activities, and were regularly kept informed about BlueRev's progress via newsletters and social media updates.

The continuous dialogue and engagement with stakeholders proved to be a powerful driver of innovation and relevance, ensuring that project outcomes were aligned with real territorial needs and challenges, and solutions were built with end users. Several best practices emerged, such as the importance of early engagement and tailored communication strategies for different stakeholder groups. The engagement activities not only contributed to building local capacity and fostering mutual learning, but also generated tangible benefits—such as the development of regionally grounded solutions, strengthened local networks, and increased awareness of the potential of the blue bioeconomy.

2 Introduction

The goal of this report is to present the status and the metrics related to the stakeholders' engagement activities carried out during the BlueRev project. This includes detailing the nature of stakeholders involved, describing the strategies employed to effectively engage with them, tracking the outcomes of their involvement and assessing the overall impact of their interactions on the project's progress.

This document builds on the work carried out within WP2, whose main objective has been, throughout the whole project's duration, to aggregate a wide range of actors — including government, industry, civil society, and local communities — to analyse social and economic barriers and potentialities along the bio-based value chain and to co-create new solutions in terms of governance, business models and social innovation.

Stakeholder engagement plays a crucial role in blue bioeconomy projects like BlueRev: the involvement of different actors, including local and regional authorities, primary biomass producers, small-medium enterprises, civil society organisations, knowledge providers and marginalised groups in project activities ensures that different perspectives, knowledge and expertise are considered, which in turn helps in addressing the multifaceted challenges of the blue bioeconomy sector.

This deliverable is structured into six chapters. Following the introduction to the work conducted under WP2, Chapter 3 explores the concept of stakeholder engagement and illustrates how this approach was implemented within BlueRev's activities. Chapter 4 presents the outcomes of stakeholder engagement, with a focus on the actions carried out throughout the project's duration. Chapter 5 highlights best practices in stakeholder engagement, while Chapter 6 concludes the report and outlines potential areas for future development.

3 Understanding stakeholders' engagement

The term “stakeholder” is generally used to describe individuals, groups, or organizations that have an interest in a certain activity and can mobilize resources to affect its outcome in some way. A commonly used definition identifies them as “individuals and organizations who are actively involved in a project, or whose interests may be positively or negatively affected as a result of project execution or successful project completion” (Project Management Institute, 1996).

In this context, stakeholders' engagement refers to the process of **actively involving stakeholders in project planning, decision-making, and execution**, and requires a comprehensive approach that includes ongoing communication, listening, and collaboration from all parties. Active stakeholder engagement is crucial to realize the benefits of sustainable bioeconomy development. In fact, while science is one important part of developing the bioeconomy, another part is to understand and guide the social change necessary for the implementation (Knierim et al. 2018).

Over its three-year duration, the BlueRev project carried out continuous stakeholder engagement by identifying relevant individuals and organizations and actively involving them in project activities. Their input was regularly gathered and discussed, and their concerns were carefully considered throughout the process.

The interactive innovation model on which the project was based is the **multi-actor approach (MAA)**, an approach that “calls all relevant actors with complementary backgrounds and expertise – scientific, practical and other – to co-create and share knowledge, best practices and innovative solutions from project beginning to end” (EIP-AGRI, 2017). The use of this bottom-up approach leads to the development of innovative solutions that are more ready to be applied in practice and cover real needs. During the BlueRev project, we engaged stakeholders in co-creation activities, Living Labs, interviews and training activities.

When adopting the multi-actor approach, the key actors depend on the project's objectives. In general, they are primarily the end users of the project outcomes, supported by other important intermediaries and contributors who can offer expertise

and innovative ideas, and can play a role in communicating and disseminating results, ultimately demonstrating the project's achievements. The 'co-creation' process stems from the fact that building blocks for the project are expected to come from science as well as from practice. In the bioeconomy context, a stakeholder may be any actor – institution, group or individual – who:

- a. has the power/ability to make a real change towards the implementation of the bioeconomy (instrumental), e.g. policymakers
- b. holds valuable information or knowledge for the issue at hand (substantive), e.g. scientists
- c. is directly or indirectly affected by the planning and implementation of the bioeconomy (normative), e.g., farmers and citizens (Rodriguez & Strøm, 2020).

*Deliverable D3.3: "KPIs and tools for selecting good practice methods"*¹ gives a broad overview of methodologies and indicators to measure the effectiveness of stakeholder engagement, inclusivity, and co-creation depth (e.g., Quadruple Helix adoption).

3.1 Stakeholders' engagement in BlueRev

BlueRev selected a range of systems in the blue bio-based sector in three different pilot regions throughout Europe, i.e. Denmark and Greenland, Italy and Estonia, to analyse their social and economic barriers and potentialities, to develop and replicate governance, business and social innovation models, to enable sufficient impacts and performances of the specific value chains and to allow replication across Europe.

One of its main objectives is hence to engage local communities of stakeholders to revitalise them both in a territorial and social sense and enhance awareness and communication between them about opportunities for collaboration along the bio-based value chain. Since the mobilisation of stakeholders represents a necessary condition to reach the BlueRev objectives, the active involvement of these stakeholders has been a

¹ 10.5281/zenodo.15877789

primary action throughout the project. The stakeholders involved came different categories:

- a. Local and regional authorities
- b. Primary biomass producers
- c. Small-medium enterprises
- d. Civil society organisations, including NGOs
- e. Knowledge providers
- f. Community knowledge
- g. Marginalised groups

These stakeholders have been targeted by the consortium at the beginning of the project and involved throughout the whole project's life through a stakeholders' board (SB). This board, whose structure has been extensively described in *D2.1 - Stakeholders' board structure, communication tools and rules*², was intended as a database of stakeholders to be actively engaged in project activities, and with the potential to act as important multipliers.

The main activities in which stakeholders were actively involved included:

- Workshops and interviews for the analysis of pilot regions (WP3)
- Co-creation workshops for elaboration of new solutions (WP4)
- Demonstration workshops to present the project's results (WP5)
- A tailored training programme to increase skilled jobs opportunities and small-scale establishments in the bio-based sector (WP5).

These activities are described in detail in Chapter 4.

3.2 Stakeholders' engagement strategy

² [10.5281/zenodo.7378172](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7378172)

The stakeholders' engagement process within BlueRev started with an exercise of stakeholders' identification conducted during the project's kick-off meeting and described in *D2.1 - Stakeholders' board structure, communication tools and rules*. Once the most relevant categories of stakeholders were identified, they were engaged in different ways:

- a. In a first phase, **all project partners (and especially in the pilot regions) involved stakeholders from their networks by using their channels**. This allowed to populate the SB leveraging on partners' broad and well-established connections, previous contacts established by the consortium members in previous projects and activities, as well as from publicly available contacts.
- b. **Engagement of new stakeholders through social media posts** in collaboration with the communication team: these were aimed at inviting people to subscribe to the project's newsletter, consult the website, and stay updated on the latest news and events related to BlueRev and the blue bioeconomy world.

Why should you get involved in the #BlueRevEU? 🌊💡
To make a difference in your region, and build a #sustainable future together! 🌱🌍
📄 Fill in the form and be part of our activities or join the stakeholder board. ... altro

Vedi traduzione

Figure 1: Example of social media post on LinkedIn

- c. **The use of the Support Tool (BlueRev Support Tool)** increased stakeholders' engagement, especially during the second phase of the project, when trainings, webinars and scientific publications were uploaded, attracting new visitors and subscribers. The Support Tool represents a great channel to get stakeholders closer, as it trains stakeholders, allows collaboration and document exchange and enhances cooperation opportunities.

- d. **The synergy with sister projects and other related projects**, including the participation in the same events and interaction on each other's platforms, maximized the outreach and drew in new stakeholders. The most significant achievement of this collaboration was the organization of a joint final conference with three other projects connected to BlueRev in different ways.

All the stakeholders engaged through the above-mentioned channels have been added to the SB regularly, to have a comprehensive view of the metrics reached and the categories involved over the course of the project.

3.2.1 Registration forms/feedback forms

To keep track of stakeholders' participation before events or workshops and collect their impressions afterwards, registration forms and feedback forms were used:

- a. **Registration forms** allowed to collect essential details of participants, enabling easy communication before, during, and after the event (e.g., sending reminders, updates, and follow-ups). The forms were tailored to each specific event and provided information on data processing and storage within the project, in accordance with the GDPR rules. Participants could fill in the forms by using links or QR codes.
- b. **Feedback forms** were used to gather responses and opinions from participants after events and workshops. Their primary objective was to assess stakeholders' satisfaction and gather suggestions for future meetings.

4 Outcomes of stakeholders' engagement

The activities carried out during the project resulted in the involvement of almost **1000 actors overall**. This number reflects the total participations across the different activities; however, some individuals are counted multiple times, as they participated in initial activities and later re-engaged due to their sustained interest in the project and its ongoing developments.

At the same time, the project's Stakeholders Board provides a complementary perspective, as each stakeholder is included only once, resulting in 518 unique contacts. While this ensures a clear overview of distinct stakeholders, it does not fully capture the project's overall outreach. In fact, several participants did not provide consent to be inserted in the SB, including many students who were involved only in a second phase of the project through training activities.

Consequently, the total number of individuals reached by the project exceeds the number formally recorded in the Stakeholders Board, due both to repeated engagement over time and to the lack of consent from some participants to be included in the database.

Figure 2 provides an overview of the stakeholders' categories involved in project's activities:

Figure 2: Type of stakeholders involved in BlueRev activities

They were involved in different activities across the project's life:

- **Several workshops and interviews** in WP3 and WP4, aiming at facilitating dialogue among local stakeholders in each pilot region. From the outset, each pilot region conducted preliminary research to identify regional challenges and opportunities within the blue bio-based industry. These insights were shared during co-creation workshops, where stakeholders collaboratively explored potential solutions using tools such as design thinking, mind mapping, and SWOT analysis.
- **Four successful pilot regions demonstration** in WP5, where the best practices and solutions developed within the project were presented to all stakeholders under a fully transferable case-study approach. During these demonstrations, opportunities provided by the blue bioeconomy in each region were explored, and valuable networking opportunities were created to foster collaboration and strengthen partnerships.
- **A training programme** focusing on helping local stakeholders to develop skilled jobs and small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy, thus helping to revitalise local communities and raise awareness of bio-based options: this programme was targeted to association of producers, master and PhD students.
- **Communication activities**, including social media interaction, project's newsletters, participation in external events.

Another occasion to engage stakeholders was the BlueRev final conference, organized as a joint event with three related projects (**BlueBioClusters**, **BlueRev**, **Engage4BIO** - cluster 6, blue-bio economy and circular economy - and **SKILLBILL** - cluster 5, renewable energy), where participation was high and diverse, as shown in *Figure 3*:

6. Can you indicate your sector of belonging?

● Academia	35
● Industry	21
● Civil society, including NGOs	13
● Policymaker	17
● Altro	34

5. Are you a team member of the organizing projects?

● No	59
● Yes, BlueRev	14
● Yes, BBC	17
● Yes, Engage4Bio	17
● Yes, SkillBill	13

Figure 3: Final conference – stakeholders' category

The final conference (*Figure 3*), with over 85 participants, included a strong presence of stakeholders external to the four consortia (notably SMEs from Estonia and Italy involved in BlueRev, and one SME from Estonia for BBC), underlying the high interest and the exploitation impact of the event; the conference created a dynamic space for exchange between researchers, practitioners, policymakers, and civil society actors.

The paragraphs below explain in detail the nature of stakeholders involved, as well as engagement metrics for all the above-mentioned activities.

4.1 Stakeholders engaged

In the BlueRev project, partners were able to put together the interaction from across the quadruple helix (academia-industry-government-civil), to obtain reliable, trusted and

taken up results by society, considering the inclusivity of the engagement by diversity of participation. This collaborative framework can better support sustainable development, ensuring that solutions are socially responsible, economically viable, and environmentally sound. Below is given a detailed description of the stakeholders who contributed to BlueRev results:

- **Local and regional authorities:** each pilot region engaged with municipalities, ministries and regional representatives. Being directly connected to the communities they serve, they had a clear understanding of local needs, challenges, and opportunities.
- **Primary biomass producers,** including seafood processors, algae producers and fish producers, and exporters.
- **Small-medium enterprises and start-ups** in the algae and cosmetic field.
- **Civil society organisations:** pilot regions engaged with associations of local entrepreneurs, cultural centers (e.g., preserving local maritime traditions) and NGOs (e.g., promoting sustainable use of marine living resources and marine protection). Civil society's involvement ensures that the voices of communities are heard and that solutions reflect the needs and values of a broader population, not just elite or specialized groups.
- **Knowledge providers,** including high education institutions, academia representatives and vocational education institutions such as regional training centers.
- **Marginalised groups:** they play an essential role during discussions because their perspectives are often overlooked, yet they are deeply affected by policies and societal issues. Their inclusion ensures that decision-making processes are more equitable, inclusive, and responsive to the diverse needs of society.

According to the *Report on Cohesion Policy and Marginalised Communities* there is no general definition of marginalised communities by the European Commission, but Member States have the responsibility of deciding on a definition on the basis of their national indicators; however, marginalisation can be established by looking at a set of relevant indicators such as **social exclusion, high long-term unemployment, a low level of education, (extremely) poor housing conditions, a high level of discrimination, and excessive exposure to health risks and/or lack of access to healthcare** (Report - A8-0314/2015).

In the BlueRev project, different types of marginalised groups were engaged:

- a. the Estonian hub engaged several **students from local high schools** in the Saaremaa region, an island characterized by higher-than-average youth unemployment, NEET youth, and high youth outmigration. The invitation to participate in the co-creation workshop in Saaremaa in February 2023 was disseminated through the local high school, vocational school and college in Saaremaa, and was supported by the local newspaper that published an article on the opportunities of blue bioeconomy and the information on the upcoming workshop. The youth participants provided valuable input to the discussions on the outlook of blue bioeconomy training and entrepreneurship in the region, highlighting the barriers and potential solutions from their perspective. They addressed topics such as youth outmigration, attractiveness of the blue bioeconomy sector, awareness among young people of local fishing and culinary traditions, the coverage of blue bioeconomy topics in high school and the availability of trainings in the local vocational school.
- b. In Greenland, **people living in the settlements**, who encounter numerous social issues, including difficulties related to housing, transportation, and essential facilities, were indirectly engaged in the BlueRev activities. These individuals were not directly interviewed and did not actively participate in workshops partly due to language barriers and logistical constraints. However, their perspectives were represented through the involvement of *Royal Greenland*, a company with more than 30 production sites across different settlements, which was actively

involved in the events in June 2024 and June 2025 and in the preparatory analysis prior to the workshops. Furthermore, people living in the settlements were directly involved during company visits, as many of them are employed in the local production facilities visited within the framework of the project. In Greenland, logistics is a challenge, and recruiting participants to onsite events is difficult as it is not possible to drive from one town or settlement to another: for this reason, people not living in the capital have to travel by plane or ship and stay in a hotel, which can be costly and time-consuming.

- c. The Italian region, thanks to its strong connection with the local municipality, was involved in a local project, G.E.S.T.I (Young Energies for Territorial Development and Innovation)³, managed by **the counseling center for families**, aimed at involving vulnerable people in new business activities. This project aims to extend social protection services and support for families and young people, to prevent youth emigration from Sicily and broader Italy due to limited employment opportunities. In this context, the University of Palermo presented the BlueRev project and blue economy opportunities, specifically highlighting potential for new SMEs focused on marine residual biomass valorization and blue biotechnologies. In this frame, the Italian hub, thanks to the University of Palermo, collaborated with the Beehive⁴ initiative, a social enterprise dedicated to creating value and retaining talent in Southern Italy, where meaningful employment opportunities combining scientific expertise with professional development remain scarce. During the BlueRev project meeting in September 2024, connected to the G7 participation, both projects presented their outputs, and stakeholders explored concrete pathways for integrating blue economy principles into regional development strategies, positioning marine biotechnology as a

³ <https://www.comune.marsala.tp.it/it/eventi/progetto-gesti>

⁴ <https://www.beehivesud.it/en>

viable solution for both environmental challenges and youth employment in the region.

4.2 Workshops/interviews

The majority of workshops and interviews within the project were conducted under WP3 and WP4.

Under WP3, engagement activities included in-depth discussions on social and economic barriers and potential opportunities to enable the transition of pilot regions towards socially and environmentally responsible behaviour. A methodology was developed to assess the effectiveness of the existing governance framework in the pilot regions, i.e., the schemes, processes, and principles organising and surrounding the cases. To this scope, workshops and interviews took place in each pilot region, ultimately engaging 174 stakeholders. Stakeholders' distribution by category and by country is shown in *Figure 4* and *Figure 5*:

Figure 4: WP3 interviews and workshops - stakeholders' category

Figure 5: WP3 interviews and workshops – stakeholders by region

More details on the distribution of stakeholders in each pilot region and their contribution during the workshops are provided in *Annex 1*.

The information gathered through the above activities was used to co-create new solutions for business models and governance structures, as well as models for social innovations, to boost local development through the potentialities offered by the bio-based sector, in an iterative process of interaction. In each pilot region, a variety of different stakeholders participated in the workshops, for a total of 95 actors engaged, distributed as follows:

Figure 6: WP4 workshops - stakeholders' category

Figure 7: WP4 workshops - stakeholders by region

More details on the distribution of stakeholders in each pilot region and their contribution during the workshops are provided in *Annex 2*.

4.3 Pilot regions demonstration workshops

Demonstration workshops in the three pilot regions showcased the solutions developed in WP4, explored case studies in depth and presented the project results, engaging a diverse group of relevant stakeholders. They served not only as platforms for knowledge sharing but also as opportunities for networking, collaboration, and the integration of local bio-based economy initiatives into the broader transition toward a sustainable bioeconomy. The four demonstration workshops brought together 174 participants (single users) in total. *Figure 8* and *Figure 9* show the distribution of stakeholders by category and by country for the four events:

Figure 8: WP5 demonstration workshops – stakeholders by category

Figure 9: WP5 demonstration workshops – stakeholders by country

The stakeholder composition in *Figure 8* provides valuable insights into engagement patterns and project impact. It is worth mentioning that the categories indicated have been grouped based on this definition:

- a. **Academia** includes researchers, professors and academic experts
- b. **Students** include bachelor, master and PhD students
- c. **Industry** includes all economic and business actors in the private sector
- d. **Public sector** includes government bodies, public authorities, regulators and local municipalities
- e. **Civil society** includes non-profit organizations, associations, foundations and third sector organizations
- f. **Other** includes other backgrounds.

Academic participation was notably high in Estonia and Italy, where the organizing research institutions (EMU and UNIPA) leveraged their extensive networks to promote the workshops within their academic communities. This academic engagement is crucial for ensuring the scientific rigor and knowledge transfer aspects of the project.

However, the significant participation of enterprises and private sector representatives across all regions—consistently representing the second-largest stakeholder group—indicates market interest in the co-developed solutions. This enterprise engagement is particularly encouraging as it suggests that small and medium enterprises (SMEs) recognize the commercial potential and practical value of the BlueRev innovations. Their active presence during the workshops demonstrates their commitment to being part of the sustainable transformation process.

The cross-sectoral participation observed across all workshops creates valuable opportunities for knowledge cross-contamination between different stakeholder categories. The interaction between academic researchers, private enterprises, public authorities, and civil society organizations facilitates the development of comprehensive solutions that address both technical and socio-economic challenges in the blue bioeconomy. This multi-stakeholder engagement is directly aligned with the project's exploitation activities and commercialization strategy. The presence of public authorities alongside private sector representatives creates an optimal environment for discussing regulatory frameworks, funding opportunities, and policy support mechanisms necessary for scaling the developed solutions. Furthermore, the involvement of local municipalities

ensures that the solutions are grounded in regional realities and can be effectively integrated into local development strategies.

This broad representation created a rich and multidisciplinary environment that supported meaningful exchanges under the umbrella of the project.

4.4 Training programme

A high level of engagement was also reached thanks to the training activities conducted in the second part of the project. The trainings were conducted by three partners: the University of Palermo (UNIPA), the Estonian University of Life Sciences (EMÜ) and the Agency for the Promotion of European Research (APRE). Additional details on training can be found in D5.2- Training programme and materials⁵, D5.3-Lessons recordings and related materials⁶.

4.4.1 Training programme: EMÜ

EMÜ conducted various trainings aimed at increasing small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy and skilled job opportunities. The target participants were master and PhD students in agro-food technology, economy, bioeconomy and associations of producers (fishermen, fish processors, algae growers/collectors/processors).

The trainings were divided into five separate modules offered as both full elective courses at the university and as a standalone training event in the Saaremaa region and involved a total number of **109 stakeholders**. *Figure 10* shows the distribution of participants:

⁵ 10.5281/zenodo.14353832

⁶ 10.5281/zenodo.15878391

Figure 10: Trainings by EMU - participants

More details on the trainings conducted in the Estonian hub can be found in *Annex 3*.

4.4.2 Training programme: UNIPA

UNIPA conducted nine trainings, including:

- Three lessons on best practices for characterisation and selection of fish by-products (FBP) and co-products (FCP) from fishery, aquaculture and processing plant, to be applied at the industrial level.
- Three lessons on methods for the extraction of bioactive compounds from FBP and FCP (from pilot to industrial scale).
- Three lessons on valorisation of bioactive compounds from FBP and FCP in cosmetics, nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals.

Target participants included associations of producers (fishermen, fish processors, algae growers/collectors/processors), as well as master and PhD students in chemistry, biochemistry, marine biotechnology and similar subjects. A total of **234 actors** were engaged in this activity:

Figure 11: Trainings by UNIPA – participants

Details on the training sessions by UNIPA can be found in *Annex 4*.

4.4.3 Training programme: APRE

APRE conducted four webinars, which fall under a broader training program aimed to empower small businesses with the knowledge, tools and practical examples of how to effectively communicate innovation in the bioeconomy sector when addressing consumers. The audience was diverse, including both students and researchers, associations of producers, policymakers, business representatives, civil society.

The single webinars were uploaded on the BlueRev Support Tool and covered different topics:

- Introduction to the concepts of communication and innovation in the bioeconomy sector
- How to write an effective communication plan
- Barriers in the bioeconomy sector
- Communicating innovations: examples from the BlueRev project

Five training sessions conducted during the G7 side event in Sicily and the demonstration workshops across the pilot regions, leading to an engagement of **203 actors**.

Figure 12: Trainings by APRE – participants

More people were reached thanks to the upload of the webinars on the project's platform. Details can be found in *Annex 5*.

Overall, the trainings performed by the different organizations successfully engaged **547 stakeholders** with different backgrounds and expertise. The upload of all the material on the Support Tool further amplified the outreach. More details on the structure and content of the training programme is available in *D5.1 – Training programme and materials*⁷ and *D5.3 – Lessons recordings and related materials*⁸.

⁷ 10.5281/zenodo.14353832

⁸ 10.5281/zenodo.15878391

5 Lessons learnt from stakeholders' engagement

Since the BlueRev kick-off, stakeholders' involvement and feedback have proven essential to the project's development and impact. Specifically:

- Feedback from public authorities provided critical guidance on balancing sustainability goals with economic development, helping to shape strategies that support local employment and infrastructure.
- The involvement of SMEs and start-ups allowed for practical and innovative insights into the commercial viability and future potential of blue bioeconomy initiatives, such as product ideas like omega-3-enriched beverages discussed in *D4.4 – A best practice guideline including the best practices coming from the three pilot regions*⁹.
- Input from fish processors and producers played a key role in optimizing sustainable sourcing and supply chain efficiency, while also fostering circular economy practices by exploring value-added uses for by-products.
- Importantly, the engagement of marginalized groups helped ensure the project addressed broader social objectives, promoting inclusiveness, community empowerment, and long-term social cohesion.
- Bringing together companies with similar activities or businesses, along with actors from other parts of the value chain, in facilitated workshops was highly valuable for both the industry and local communities. These workshops indeed provided a platform for developing new ideas, discussing alternative business models, and exploring potential collaborations. The facilitation process became even more effective when stakeholders were interviewed beforehand, allowing their challenges and suggestions to be addressed more directly.

Several best practices emerged from this process. First of all, **early involvement of stakeholders** was particularly effective in building trust and encouraging active commitment to the project's objectives. Secondly, **communication strategies tailored**

⁹ 10.5281/zenodo.1473133

to the interests and backgrounds of different stakeholder groups—ranging from public authorities to SMEs, fish producers, and marginalized communities—helped maintain consistent and meaningful participation. Involving this diversity was crucial to address the complexity of the blue bioeconomy and ensure that solutions were both socially inclusive and practically viable. The **use of participatory tools**, such as design thinking workshops, mind mapping sessions, and SWOT analyses, encouraged inclusive dialogue and supported collaborative decision-making.

The main takeaway from the activities conducted is that stakeholder engagement requires careful planning, diverse resources, and the flexibility to adapt to stakeholder feedback and changing local conditions. When these elements are in place, engagement activities are more likely to generate meaningful participation, increase the relevance of project outcomes and contribute to tangible, lasting results.

Sustainable innovation in the blue bio-based sector must be rooted in collaborative value creation, where stakeholders are engaged not just as beneficiaries but as co-creators of solutions. A participatory approach indeed fosters trust, strengthens the relevance of innovations, and creates a foundation for scaling models responsibly and inclusively.

6 Conclusions

The stakeholder engagement activities carried out throughout the BlueRev project proved to be essential in shaping inclusive, impactful, and locally grounded outcomes.

The active involvement of around 1000 stakeholders (more than 518 unique contacts) from various sectors was key to meeting BlueRev's objectives. Through workshops, interviews, training sessions, demonstration events, and communication efforts, BlueRev facilitated dialogue among diverse stakeholders, enabling the identification of region-specific barriers and opportunities, and the co-development of innovative, responsible social innovation measures, business models and governance structures. The engagement strategies, ranging from co-creating solutions to fostering networking opportunities, enabled stakeholders to build trust, share knowledge, and collaborate effectively.

The three pilot region demonstrations represented crucial moments to showcase project outcomes and share transferable solutions, creating opportunities for stakeholders to form meaningful connections and explore potential collaborations. In parallel, the training program empowered local actors with practical skills to engage in the bioeconomy, supporting job creation, community revitalization, and long-term sustainability. Communication efforts further strengthened visibility and connection, extending the project's reach and reinforcing engagement.

Overall, meaningful stakeholder involvement integrated across all project phases, enhanced the relevance of BlueRev's initiatives and fostered collaboration, hence contributing to positive social and environmental impacts and enhancing awareness of collaboration opportunities across the bio-based value chain.

7 References

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Annex 1 – WP3 activities

Hub	Workshop / interview	Actors involved	Details (topic, type of stakeholder..)
Italy	Semi structured interviews	17	Collection of data from policy makers, academia, associations, industries and relevant actors in the private sector, producing and processing fish and derived products.
Italy	Co-creation workshop in presence	2	Workshop conducted during the event “Maritime day in my country”, with representatives from the private sector.
Italy	Meeting in presence	9	Regular meetings with the companies involved in the LCA study.
Italy	Co-creation workshop in presence	15	Workshop on innovative governance with local stakeholders.
Estonia	Interview - Online and in presence	6	Collection of data from relevant actors in the industry sector, policymakers, researchers, and development centers.
Estonia	Co-creation workshop - in presence	94	A workshop was conducted with the world cafe methodology, aimed at collecting data and presenting obstacles and possible solutions in the region.
Estonia	Co-creation workshop	18	Development of a vision for the blue-bioeconomy in the region; group discussion on governance and social innovation issues.
Denmark - Greenland	Interviews online	12	Interviews covered perspectives from the private sector, business associations, and government institutions.
Denmark - Greenland	Interviews online	1	Collection of data for the LCA study and involvement of Greenlandic industries.

Annex 2 – WP4 workshops

Hub	Actors involved	Details
Italy	8	Stakeholders and experts from the fishing industry were involved to gather inputs for the development of the governance recommendations (D4.3).
Denmark	11	Different stakeholders provided input on governance recommendations (D4.3) and business model development (D4.2).
Greenland	19	Different stakeholders provided input on governance recommendations (D4.3) and business model development (D4.2).
Estonia	32	Different stakeholders provided inputs in terms of governance recommendations (D4.3).
Estonia	10	Enterprise representatives, research institutions and local government officials provided inputs for business model development (D4.2).
Estonia	15	Enterprise representatives, research institutions and a non-profit organization provided inputs for business model development (D4.2).

Annex 3 – EMU training programme

Date	Format	Participants	Title	Details
20/09/24	In presence	5	Module 1 - Blue bioeconomy: concept, drivers and SDGs	Bachelor, master and PhD students
11/10/24	In presence	4	Module 2 - Maritime planning and policy context for blue bioeconomy	Bachelor, master and PhD students
01/11/24 13/03/25 27/03/25 14/04/25	In presence – four sessions	50	Module 3 - Innovation in blue bioeconomy	Bachelor, master and PhD students
22/11/24	In presence	4	Module 4. Collaboration models for sustainable blue bioeconomy in rural context	Bachelor, master and PhD students
13/12/24 10/01/25	In presence – two sessions	8	Module 5 - Social and governance innovation in blue bioeconomy	Bachelor, master and PhD students
28/08/25	Hybrid	38	Blue bioresource valorization and new development possibilities.	Enterprises, non-profit associations, public sector, and academic faculty

Annex 4 – UNIPA training programme

Date	Format	Participants	Title	Details
06/11/24 – two sessions	Hybrid	46	Extractions on bioactive molecules from marine by-products: from pilot to industrial scale	Masters and PhD students
07/11/24 – two sessions	Hybrid	71	Circular economy for aquatic productions valorization of bioactive compounds in cosmetics, nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals	Masters and PhD students
21/11/24	In presence	19	The living lab experience for circular economy application in Sicily	Associations of producers
21/11/24	In presence	19	Demonstrative activities for quality assessment and extraction of marine bioactive compounds: from theory to practice	Masters and PhD students
9/12/24	Hybrid	23	Extractions on bioactive molecules from marine by-products, from pilot to industrial scale: focus on proteic components and antioxidants	Masters and PhD students
19/03/25	Hybrid	20	Circular Economy in the Fishery Value-Chain: Focus on Extraction and Valorization (Training supported by <i>Site Universitaire du Creusot</i> -	International Masters students

			Université Bourgogne Europe and FORTHEM European alliance)	
7/05/25	In presence	18	Field training: Innovation and sustainability in the fish supply chain	Master-PhD students from UNIPA and International academy network (Forthem Alliance)
23/07/25	In presence	11	Field training: innovation and sustainability in the fish processing supply chain	Representatives from academia, researchers, enterprises manager and technicians
30/07/2025	In presence	7	Field training in fish processing facilities	Representatives from academia, researchers, enterprises manager and technicians

Annex 5 – APRE training programme

Date	Format	N° Participants	Title	Details
26/09/24	In presence - G7 Agriculture	29	How to communicate innovation in the bioeconomy sector when addressing consumers	Associations of producers, fishermen, companies' representatives, policymakers, and researchers.
02/04/25	In presence - Saaremaa	53		Policymakers, business representatives, fishermen, and researchers.
29/04/25	Online	17		Public institutions, businesses, associations and foundations, as well as academia.
29/05/25	In presence - Sicily	90		Public institutions, businesses, associations, academia, and fishermen.
17/06/25	In presence - Nuuk	14		Businesses, policy representatives, and civil society

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